

Low Cost Rural Housing MALAWI - June 2022

Deliberate Government of Malawi strategy is the only viable solution to Low Cost Rural and Semi-urban Housing Project in Malawi as part of fulfilling Sustainable Development Goals

By

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Project Description

Upgrade traditional housing (huts) in Malawi into durable, comfortable and affordable dwelling places befitting human occupancy in line with universal human rights. The project intends to involve the abundance of the local materials to reduce the burden on the foreign currency exchange reserves. Furthermore, the project intends to explore innovative financing products which will stir rural economic growth by creating rural growth centres.

Current Problem

The Malawian Population Census (2018:32) averred:

[There were 4,805,431 housing units enumerated in the 2018 PHC as shown in Table 4.2. Of these housing units, 41.1

percent were permanent, 23.0 percent were semi-permanent and 35.9 percent were traditional. In the Northern Region, 53.9 percent of housing units were permanent, 26.3 percent were semi-permanent and 35.9 percent were traditional. For Central Region, 33.6 percent of housing units were permanent, 22.1 percent were semi-permanent and 44.3 percent were traditional. Southern Region had 45.1 percent permanent housing units, 23.1 percent semi-permanent and 31.8 percent traditional housing units.].

The data above indicates Malawi had about 1,730,000 traditional houses which are susceptible to leaking as they are grass thatched, heavily infested with bedbugs, maggots, ants, termites and some troublesome parasites but also vulnerable to adverse climatic conditions such as cyclones which come with strong winds and heavy rains. About 7,000,000 Malawians live in such miserable conditions. The pictures and videos concerning these dwelling places are indeed soul-breaking but little seems to have been done yet different initiatives have been tried albeit with minimal results.

The semi-permanent housing units are usually constructed using unburnt bricks or those with burnt bricks but not mortar from cement components. These are dangerous structures prone to climatic calamities such as cyclones and prolonged rains. 1,105,000 houses fall into this category bringing about additional 4,420,000 in potential harm's way. Therefore about 11,420,000 Malawians were dwelling in dangerous

Houses in 2018. This is a worrisome trend as Malawian population is projected to reach 26,000,000 million in 2030 - Why Population Matters to Malawi's Development (2012) and therefore more people are likely to live in undesirable houses if deliberate interventions are not sought now.

Government initiative from 1964 to 2022

The Late Dr Ngwazi H Kamuzu Banda, the first Malawian President was emphasizing on adequate food, decent clothing and decent houses which do not leak. The housing issue has not materialised in view of the growing poverty over the last thirty years.

Malawi Poverty Reduction Strategy Paper (2002) did not cover matters regarding housing and so was Malawi Economic Growth Strategy (2003). Malawi Growth and Development Strategy (2006-2011) covered matters of housing under Theme One Sub Theme Six: Land and Housing and it stated the shortfalls of Malawi Poverty Reduction Strategy Paper (2002) and Malawi Economic Growth Strategy on this subject matter. Malawi Growth and Development Strategy (2006:91/92) conducive framework for improved access to adequate housing services was one of the outcomes (Medium Term Expected) of Theme One Sub Theme Six and this included development of National Housing Policy with the following Key Actions:

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- Develop the National Housing Policy
- Lobby Government and stakeholders to appreciate the role of housing in poverty reduction
- Review the 1999 National Housing Policy to re-align it to Government policies and protocols
- Encourage stakeholders to mobilize resources to meet housing demands, particularly low-income/ vulnerable households
- Encourage lending institutions to formulate funding schemes for the most vulnerable groups
- Review the draft Building Regulations and Standards, and conduct research in building materials
- Promote labour intensive construction methods to generate jobs
- Promote civic education and social mobilization campaigns
- Promote and encourage community participation in infrastructure provision and maintenance
- Conduct civic education on housing, available housing programmes and/or housing delivery systems.
- Encourage communities to form housing and multi-purpose community development cooperatives,

Much is not known about the level of the attainability of the Key Actions above. Malawi Growth and Development Strategy II (2012:14) however provided a summary of the subject matter:

[Housing and Urban Development: Achievements registered under this sub-sector include the following: maintained houses under government lease, constructed Government

Offices; conducted quinquennial valuations and supplementary valuation rolls; decentralized the Rural Housing Programme; commenced a National Slum Upgrading Programme; and developed Guidelines on Safer House Construction. In addition, Malawi Housing Corporation (MHC) continued to construct houses.].

It was obvious that not much was done on addressing matters regarding traditional housing structures and poverty prevalent in the rural areas between 2006 and 2011. Theme Four Sub Theme 5 of Malawi Growth and Development Strategy II (2012:58) - Infrastructure Development strived to address the problem and annotated as follows:

[Good housing contributes to economic growth and poverty reduction. It adds to the reduction of the health burden from infectious and parasitic diseases and accidents. It also provides security and is a large asset base and a source of income.

The nation has a large housing deficit. The 2008 Population and Housing Census indicates that out of 2,869,933 houses, 21.4 percent were permanent, 34.18 percent were semipermanent while 44.42 percent were classified as traditional. The Malawi Urban Housing Profile of 2009 revealed that to meet the housing demands in the urban areas, there is a need to construct 21,000 houses per year for a period of ten years. This, therefore, means that the majority of Malawians are living in houses that are not decent.

Goal

The goal is to increase access to decent housing with particular attention to low income households.].

Dr Joyce Banda, Former President of the Republic of Malawi rolled out Mudzi Transformation Trust in 2013 using non-state funds to build houses for rural and peri-urban poor which proved popular especially among potential female voters and was branded a campaign tool by the opposition but nevertheless managed to deliver 500 houses by end of 2013 - Hamer and Seekings (2017). The Mudzi Transformation Trust included distribution of cows and was included in the People's Party 2014 Manifesto for the 2014 Tripartite Elections. The subsequent regime of Democratic Progressive Party (DPP) which was previously in power between 2005 and 2012 decided to incorporate the rural and peri-urban housing assistance dubbed Decent and Affordable Housing Subsidy Programme (DAHSP) into mainstream government function as noted by Chimjeka (2021):

[DAHSP, popularly known as Malata and Cement Subsidy Programme, is a Democratic Progressive Party signature programme designed to build 66,000 units for the poor—70 houses in each of the country's 193 constituencies—on a 50 percent subsidy every year.

Five thousand of the units were supposed to be grants to the ultra-poor. The total cost of the project, which was planned to

for five years—from 2014 to 2019— was K39 billion.].

Kasanda (2021) provided further details of the DAHSP package as follows:

[The ministry has indicated that, from 2015 to 2019, at least 37,781 beneficiaries were reached out to. However, out of these, 22,440 had their house fully rehabilitated while others are still waiting for materials to complete rehabilitation works.

The DAHSP was meant to benefit resource-constrained people by giving them material loans that would enable them to acquire a maximum of 30 corrugated iron sheets of 29/30 gauge of 10 feet each and a maximum of 30 bags of cement of 50 kilogrammes each and related building materials.]

Chimjeka (2021) reported that Ministry of Lands had commenced forensic audit on DAHSP as only MWK110 million out of MWK14 billion disbursements had been collected. Kasanda (2021) reported a month later that MWK148 million had been collected out of MWK6.3 billion which was overdue and the balance would mature in 2024. The high default rate was partly blamed on some politicians who were misleading beneficiaries that they need not to repay the loans.

The DAHSP was suspended in 2020 – Kasanda (2021) and no replacement was put in place. Sangala (2015d) earlier scribed it would be desirable to suspend the malata (iron sheets) subsidy in view of tight budgetary

resources. Sangala (2015c) noted that DAHSP was faced with failure and partial delivery such that the beneficiaries in some districts such as Blantyre had spent significant sums of money in anticipation of the materials which were not forthcoming such as door and window frames which government was supposed to provide. Sangala (2015b) observed that beneficiaries in Karonga felt cheated as they were receiving 22 iron sheets instead of the approved 30 since the loans to be repaid were pegged at 30 iron sheets. Lack of transport in Rumphi District derailed the implementation of DAHSP – Sangala (2015). Sangala (2016b) annotated that the regime declined to scrap off the DAHSP despite calls from opposition political parties and some economic commentators citing that benefits outweighed the challenges encountered. Sangala (2016a) had earlier noted that funds allocated and utilised by the programme were MWK5.8 billion in two years instead of MWK14.0 billion as approved by Parliament at MWK7.0 billion each year since 2014. There were strong allegations that the beneficiaries were being given substandard materials as Ministry of Lands Officials were pocketing the money meant for the programme – Sangala (2017). It is therefore difficult to enforce loan recovery where the lender breached the terms of the contract through supply of inadequate and substandard materials.

Malawi Growth and Development Strategy III (2017) did not cover any matters regarding housing. Malawi

Growth and Development Strategy III delayed by a year. It was supposed to have been rolled out in 2016. DAHSP was still being rolled out and failure to include such material programme in the Malawi's Medium Term Development Strategy was a substantial oversight. Malawi Growth and Development Strategy III was also replaced by Malawi Vision 2063 which under Pillar 3 (Urbanisation) of MIP 1 (2021-2030:28) stipulated the following:

[MIP-1 aims to decrease the proportion of the urban population living in informal settlements or inadequate housing from 60 percent in 2020 to 50 percent by 2030.].

The Vision 2063 has no current solutions for rural masses and that is where most traditional and semi-permanent houses are in majority in view of abject poverty in those communities. MIP 1 of Vision 2063 is prioritising construction of houses for teachers and security agents of Government of Malawi vis-à-vis Malawi Defence Force, The Malawi Police Services, Immigration Department and Malawi Prisons.

Donor funded projects

There have been several initiatives led by donors and other bilateral partners to address the acute decent housing shortage problems in Malawi. Habitat (1995) annotated as follows:

[the Malawi Rural Housing Programme attracted world-wide attention and, in 1986, won an award from the United Kingdom-based Building and Social Housing Foundation (the BSHF-IYSH Award)].

Habitat (1995) further postulated as follows:

[3.1.4. Progress and impact of the programme

As already pointed out, rural housing has generally received little attention from housing and rural development theoreticians, as well as from national policy-makers. A very significant achievement of the Malawi Rural Housing Programme is that it has demonstrated the feasibility of formulating and implementing rural housing policies and projects, even for small and relatively poor countries. As the programme progresses, the numbers of beneficiaries have been increasing, as shown in table 4 below. The planned number of beneficiaries for 1992 was 2,500. The project has been extended to all of the 24 districts in the country and the numbers of beneficiaries per annum can be expected to keep on rising.

Another significant achievement of the Malawi Rural Housing Programme, particularly from the point of view of the present discussion, is that it has demonstrated the local income-generation potential of rural housing projects through the setting up of small-scale enterprises in building construction and production of low-cost building materials.

While potential candidates were initially doubtful of these types of venture, more and more people are now being

attracted into these enterprises. By 1990, 70 entrepreneurs had been approved, while more than 40 were already in operation (Diacon, 1990, p. 15).

Table 4: Beneficiaries of the Malawi Rural Housing Programme

Year	1984	1985	1986	1989	1990	1991
No. of Beneficiaries	13	78	300	750	1,500	2,000

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Habitat II (1996) proposed 2% of Malawi's Gross Domestic Product as annual budgetary allocation for housing if Malawi would make strides in the said under-performing sector. One of the tangible outcomes of this project was the formalisation of the 1999 National Housing Policy.

Lessons from the Malawian rural housing programmes and way forward

The donor funded projects were limited in scope that is both in coverage and resources available. Perhaps there were meant to act as models for local initiatives. The government funded projects lacked monitoring and evaluation mechanisms and were therefore marred with severe irregularities which have been extensively highlighted above.

It is equally true that house construction is a substantial undertaking requiring massive resources which are not available at the disposal of impoverished households. Doing nothing to improve the habitants of the poor citizens is not optional either in view of social and health services costs exerted on the Malawi's public place as some major ailments amongst the general populace are attributed to poor accommodation and sanitation.

It is therefore recommended that Government of Malawi should initiate a rural housing programme which should alleviate suffering of its majority citizens who have no capacity to construct decent houses as most households are headed by widows, children themselves or the elderly. This is a social obligation of Government of Malawi.

Design of the rural houses under the proposed scheme

It is recommended that that there should be universal design for the rural houses so that costing mechanisms are constant, all the materials can be sourced locally and therefore have little or no impact on the foreign currency exchange reserves, pass environmental assessment protocols especially in places of quarrying and moulding of building materials, constructed in accordance with the rural planning requirements as per the amended land act, encourage numbering of houses in the villages and

therefore achieve more specific physical addresses in the rural areas but above all, the entire value chain should be controlled by indigenous citizens leading to spawning of rural growth centres and decelerate substantial urbanisation rate in Malawi which is fuelling urban poverty.

Funding mechanisms for subsequent rural housing programmes

It is a given fact that resources are scarce and inadequate to undertake such a massive project in the shortest period of time. There are however innovative funding mechanisms which are available with minimal impact on the budgetary constraints in the country's kitty. Three possible groups can be formulated as follows:

- a) Fully subsidised beneficiaries who will pay nothing based on the individual financial limitations, physical and mental challenges, age and other qualifying parameters which have to be approved on case by case bases.
- b) Partial subsidy – Government and other parties meet half of the cost of the construction and the beneficiaries advance the balance either in form of cash or agricultural produce of given quantity at specified time.
- c) No subsidy. Delivered at the full cost of the predetermined cost in exchange for cash or given

quantities of agricultural produce for which off-takers are already known and legal paperwork put in place.

Possible Funding source – Non-tax based

- a) Cannabis Sativa proceeds – a separate concept note under the INTL Forex Management provides further details.
- b) Penalties of violation on the Malawi Stock Exchange – identify potential malpractices so as fine the perpetrators to raise the funds for rural housing programmes.
- c) Penalties on the tax violation and other financial laws – citizens must take active role to ensure that tax evasion cases currently in court and those which can be commenced are timely concluded and recovered funds be used for this project.
- d) Forfeiture of proceeds of crime – mirrors the penalties for tax violations above.
- e) Press Trust Limited – a separate concept note has been prepared thereof.
- f) MACRA – it must channel some of the excess funds it has towards this noble cause. 10% of its distributable earnings each year can be channelled to the Rural Housing Fund since the telecommunication operators have towers and other equipment in the rural areas and can benefit from the levies as well.

Architectural drawings and floor maps of the proposed rural housing facilities

This is a novel idea and subject to intellectual property rights. It has therefore been presented separately from this paper.

Conclusions and recommendations

Malawi has substantial decent housing deficiency problem such that addressing rural housing debacle is not optional as quantifiable costs for inaction are far greater. This is the time to address the perennial problem (since precolonial era) through innovative financing mechanisms and creation of substantial employment opportunities as the entire value chain has to be undertaken by the indigenous rural masses. There are quality control regulations for the building materials, construction and all incidental activities which will strictly be followed at each district's council office and properly signed for to guarantee fifty years life span for each rural housing unit under the proposed programme.

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